

Effective Credit Risk Management as a Tool for Sustainable Financial Performance in Banks: A Myth or Reality?

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Abstract

Credit risk arises when a borrower fails to make loan repayments on schedule or does not comply with any contractual commitments, creating the possibility of incurring a loss. The most fundamental risk inherent to the bank's business model is credit risk. Financial institutions must manage the risk cautiously and comprehensively in order to survive in the world of high level of uncertainty. In accordance with an organization's risk principles, risk policies, risk process, and risk appetite as a continuous feature, the credit risk architecture offers the wide-ranging canvas and infrastructure to effectively identify, assess, manage, and control credit risk - both at the portfolio and individual levels. It has long been believed that the effective and efficient management of credit risk is the vital component of a broad-ranging approach to overall risk management and is fundamental to the safety and soundness of financial institutions. In the light of this thought, this research paper will try to evaluate the effectiveness of Credit Risk Management (CRM) practices of selected Indian public sector and private sector banks as a tool for improving financial performance of Indian commercial banks. For this purpose, return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), capital adequacy ratio (CAR) and net non-performing asset ratio (NPAs) has been taken into consideration to measure the efficiency of banks. The ROE and ROA are financial performance indicators whereas CAR and net NPA ratio are credit risk management indicators.

Keywords

Credit Risk Management (CRM), Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Assets(NPA).

Introduction

One of the issues facing the banking industry is credit risk management. Banks make money by providing loans to customers or businesses depending on numerous parameters. In light of the fact that lending is a major source of revenue for banks, when a borrower fails to pay off the loan, the bank is at significant risk. The 'probability of loss from a credit transaction' is the vanilla definition of Credit Risk. According to the BASEL Committee, "Credit risk is most simply defined as the potential that a borrower or counter-party will fail to meet its obligation in accordance with agreed terms". In accordance with an organization's risk principles, risk policies, risk process, and risk appetite as a continuous feature, the credit risk architecture offers the wide-ranging canvas and infrastructure to effectively identify, assess, manage, and control credit risk - both at the portfolio and individual levels. While preserving consistency and transparency, credit risk management seeks to enhance and improve the effectiveness of the banks and to protect lenders against the threat of losing money that has been credited to them. The banking sector tends to place a high priority on streamlining credit sanctioning, systematic risk management, and providing inputs for a bank-wide credit policy and set of processes. The need for more sophisticated and adaptable tools for risk management through measuring, monitoring, and limiting risk exposures is felt as banks enter a new, high-powered world of financial operations and trading, which comes with new dangers. Therefore, it becomes imperative that banks' management must be adequately prepared to handle the task of designing tools and systems that are capable of assessing, monitoring, and scientifically controlling the credit risk exposures. A holistic approach to overall risk management must include the effective and efficient management of credit risk as it is essential to the safety and soundness of financial institutions. Appropriate policies, procedures and systems should be implemented at each financial institution to effectively identify measure, monitor and control credit risk. On the grounds of above discussion, it has been figured out that Credit Risk Management is a matter of contention for all the financial institutions. In

contempt of the fact that the effective credit risk management is a significant element of intensive risk management and is crucial for the success of any financial institution in long run, it continues to be a challenge for all financial institutions. I, therefore, have chosen this topic to pay close attention to analyze the effectiveness of credit risk management practices as a tool for sound financial performance and sustainable growth of banks and to fully understand how the risks in all their business lines intersect and combine to affect the risk profile of the selected banks.

Aim of study

The primary objectives of the study are:

1. To assess and compare the financial results of selected Indian private sector banks and public sector banks.
2. To investigate the variables that influence the credit risk management practices in selected Indian commercial banks, both public and private.
3. To observe the effects of Credit Risk Management on the financial standing of the selected Indian commercial banks.

Review of Literature

Kaur, Ramanjeet (2021) in her research work "An Empirical Study of Credit Risk Management Practices of Commercial Banks in India" stated that the banks concentrate on the extent to which they expose themselves to danger and develop policies to deal efficiently with it (Cummings and Durrani, 2016). The implementation of Basel II standards and the successful implementation by RBI, in the framework of risk management procedures, are an important step which aims to encourage robust risk management methods. Therefore, it is very crucial at this juncture to reduce and contain NPAs significantly within a sensible threshold (Kopra, 2017).

Asima Siddique, Muhammad Asif Khan, Zeeshan Khan (2021) in their work "The Effect of Credit Risk Management and Bank-Specific Factors on the Financial Performance of the South Asian Commercial Banks" indicated that NPLs, CER and LR are negatively related to FP (ROA and ROE), while CAR and ALR are positively related to the FP of the Asian commercial banks. The current study results recommended that policymakers of Asian countries should create a strong financial environment by implementing the monetary policy which stimulates interest rates in such a way that automatically helps to lower down the high ratio of NPLs (tiered monitoring system).

Nikhilkumar Shah, Nisarg Shah (2020) in his work "A Credit Risk Management in Public and Private Sector Banks" contemplates that Credit risk incur due to borrower's failure to repay a loan or meet contractual obligations which creates possibilities of loss. Nonpayment of these loans and advances leads to bank crisis and perform as economic development blockage. These kinds of situation have been faced in past by world economies in term of sub-prime crisis. Thus, credit risk management in banks is important to maintain credit risk exposure within proper and acceptable parameters.

Sundarka, Baibhav P. (2020) the main findings of the study "Empirical Study of Credit Risk Management of Commercial Banks" is Credit Risk Management is becoming buzz word in today's ever dynamic business world. Modern organized Banking Firms are concentrating more on this area as an efficient strategy to gain competitive advantage. Paradigm shift in the field of banking sector has made Credit Risk Management a new frontier to gain competitive advantage. Traditional Banking practices of attracting customer through Customer Assessment and advertisements have become outdated in nature.

Nagar, Udhister (2019) "Credit risk management in commercial banks A critical study of selected public and private sector commercial bank in India" concluded that the bottom line for today's banking institutions, particularly the largest and most complex ones, is that they must continue to monitor very carefully the embedded risks of their credit products and services, pay close attention to subtle changes in business practices that could affect the risks related to a given product, and fully understand how the risks in all their business lines intersect and combine to affect the risk profile of the consolidated entity.

Dalvi Madhukar & Shelankar Mitali (2018) has measured the "Impact of Credit Risk Management on the Financial Performance of selected Public and Private Sector Banks in India". Data for study obtained by taking average of five years figures of financial performance indicator namely Net Profit Margin (NPM) and credit risk management indicators viz. Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Credit Deposit Ratio (CDR). Data has been analyzed by using Regression Model. He concluded that Public sector banks have low credit risk and negative profitability whereas private sector banks have high credit risk and high profitability.

Research gap

The findings of the study would be beneficial for banks' management, investors and other stakeholders from a practical standpoint. By minimizing credit risk, bank management can focus more on enhancing banks' performance. In light of their credit risk, banks can thus better manage their resources. Thus, present study is a significant endeavor for studying, measuring, critical thinking and reviewing the effectiveness of efficient credit risk management practices and its implications on the overall financial performance and sustainable growth of the bank.

On the basis of the research gap the following objectives and relevant hypothesis has been formulated for the purpose of the study.

Methodology

Problem Statement Effective Credit Risk Management as a Tool for Sustainable Financial Performance in Banks: A Myth or Reality? **Research Design** The study is purely based upon empirical research design. Empirical research relies on verified data to generate findings. In other words, the evidence used in this kind of research is purely based on data collected and analyzed using scientific methods. **Scope of the Study** The research work is particularly confined to three public sector banks and three private sector banks for a period of 11 years commencing from financial year 2011-12 to 2021-22.

Sampling

The sample size is 06 Banks. The sampling technique used is probabilistic sampling technique more specifically the random sampling.

Bank Profile

Bank	Year of Establishment	Capital as on 31/03/2022 Rs.('000)
SBI	1955	8,924,612
BOB	1908	10,355,336
PNB	1894	22,022,031
ICICI	1994	13,899,662
HDFC	1994	5,545,541
AXIS	1993	6,139,496

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of Selected Banks.

Sources of Data Collection

The study radically relies only on Secondary sources of information viz; annual reports, RBI Bulletin, published journals, websites, etc.

Tools Used

The tools used for analysing data are MS-Excel and SPSS.

Statistics Used in the Study

The collected data have been examined using several statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, etc. The linear regression technique has been applied to examine the relationship and determine the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables. The Independent Sample t-test and the ANOVA have also been used to test the research hypothesis and to validate the findings.

Analysis

The key variables for the problem under consideration are: Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Net Non- Performing Assets Ratio (Net NPA), Capital Adequacy Ratio to Net Non- Performing Assets Ratio (CAR/NPA).

1. ROE: The return on equity ratio (ROE), is a financial metric which measures a bank's efficiency in managing the capital that shareholders have put in it, It is a gauge of banks' profitability and how efficiently it generates those profits.
2. ROA: A bank's profitability in relation to its total assets is determined by its return on assets, or ROA Management, analysts, and investors can assess a bank's ROA to see if its resources are being used profitably.
3. CAR: The capital adequacy ratio gauges a bank's capital in relation to its current liabilities and risk-weighted assets. According to RBI standards, scheduled commercial banks should maintain a CAR of 9%, whilst Indian public sector banks are advised to maintain a CAR of 12%.

4. NPA: Banks categorize loans and advances as NPAs if the principal or interest thereon has not been paid for 90 days or more. In terms of the Net NPA to Advance ratio, the lower the ratio, the better it is, as a lower net NPA ratio is an indication of a faster recovery rate.

An in-depth analysis of all these key variables in respect of selected public sector and private sector banks has been done with the help of requisite tables and charts:

Analysis of financial performance of Indian banks

Table 1.1 : Key financial indicators of Indian public sector banks

	ROE (%)	ROA (%)	CAR (%)	NPA (%)	CAR/NPA (%)
SBI	8.66	0.49	13.31	2.69	6.12
BOB	4.63	0.30	13.65	2.89	7.54
PNB	-0.25	0.05	12.24	5.57	3.10

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

The data in table 6.1.1 depicts the key financial ratios of selected banks for the period under study. The ROE of SBI and BOB stands out at 8.66% and 4.63% respectively signifying effective capital management and generation of profits. The ROA of sample banks came out to be 0.49%, 0.30% and 0.05% for SBI, BOB and PNB respectively. The average CAR maintained by SBI, BOB and PNB is 13.31%, 13.65% and 12.24% respectively which is considered to be safe and thus, the public sector banks are in a position to meet its financial obligations. It is evident from the table that the Net NPA ratio of PNB is 5.57% indicating higher NPAs. On the other hand, the Net NPA ratio of SBI and BOB stands out at 2.69% and 2.89% respectively. The above discussion can be made clear by checking out the Chart no.1.1 below.

Source : Graphical Representation of data in Table 6.1.1

The key variables (ROE, ROA, CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA) of the selected public sector banks for the period have been illustrated with the help of different colored bars. The financial indicators of SBI, BOB and PNB have been depicted by Blue, Red and Green colored bars respectively. It is evident from the chart that SBI has highest ROE followed by BOB. On the contrary the ROE of PNB is negative. The SBI is earning highest return on assets followed by BOB and PNB. The CAR maintained by BOB is higher than that of SBI and PNB. Likewise, Net NPA of SBI and BOB is quite low as compared to that of PNB. The CAR/NPA ratio of BOB is highest followed by SBI and PNB.

Table 1.2 : Key Financial Indicators of Indian Private Sector Banks

	ROE (%)	ROA (%)	CAR (%)	NPA (%)	CAR/NPA (%)
ICICI	10.68	1.35	17.78	1.93	15.28
HDFC	18.24	1.94	16.76	0.31	58.22
AXIS	12.24	1.10	16.33	1.25	23.88

Source: All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

The data in table 6.1.2 depicts the key financial ratios of selected private sector banks for the period under study. It is evident from the table that all the banks are earning a high returns on equity but the ROE of HDFC bank is highest i.e 18.24% followed by AXIS and ICICI banks thereby managing the capital efficiently. Similarly, ROA of the banks stands out at 1.35%, 1.94% and 1.10% for ICICI, HDFC and AXIS bank. It is noticeable here that ROA of HDFCbank is higher than that of ICICI and AXIS bank. The average CAR maintained by ICICI, HDFC and AXIS banks are 17.78%, 16.76% and 16.33% respectively. A high CAR has been maintained by the banks all throughout ensuring that the banks have sufficient capital which acts like a financial cushion against losses. Among all the sample banks the Net NPA ratio of HDFC bank is lowest i.e 0.31% followed by AXIS and ICICI bank which stands out at 1.25% and 1.93% respectively. The data in Table 1.2 has been graphically plotted in Chart 1.2.

Source : Graphical Representation of data in Table 1.2

The key variables (ROE, ROA, CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA) of the selected private sector banks for the period have been illustrated with the help of different colored bars. The financial indicators of ICICI, HDFC and AXIS banks have been depicted by Blue, Yellow and Brown colored bars respectively. It is significant from the chart that HDFC bank has highest ROE (depicted by yellow color) followed by AXIS bank and ICICI bank (depicted by brown and blue color respectively). Likewise, the ROA of HDFC bank is significantly more than the return on assets earned by ICICI and AXIS bank which is 1.94%, 1.35% and 1.10% respectively. There is no significant difference in the CAR of the private sample banks. However, the yellow color of the bars signifies that HDFC bank has minimum NPA ratio i.e 0.31% and maximum CAR/NPA ratio which is 58.22% .

2.2 Analysis of impact of credit risk management on ROE of Indian banks

The impact of credit risk management on ROE of Indian banks for the period under study has been examined with the help of the following equation:

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times CAR1 + \beta_2 \times NPA1 + \beta_3 \times CAR/NPA1 + e_1$$

Where,

ROE = Return on Equity of Indian Banks for the period of 2012-2022,

CAR = Capital Adequacy Ratio for the period of 2012-22,

NPA = Non Performing Assets ratio for the period of 2012-22,

CAR/NPA = Capital Adequacy Ratio to Non -Performing Assets for the period of 2012-22,

β_0 = Intercept (Constant),

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = The slope representthe degree with which bank's performance changes as the independent variable changes by one unit of variable,

e_1 = error component.

Table 2.1 : Descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
ROE	9.03	6.38	6
CAR	15.01	2.23	6
NPA	2.44	1.81	6
CAR/NPA	19.02	20.62	6

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

The descriptive statistics of variables such as ROE, CAR, NPA, and CAR/NPA calculated from the dataset of 06 private and public sector banks in India for a period of 11 years beginning from 2012 are shown in Table 2.1. The number of observations for each variable is 264. The mean value of dependent variable (ROE) is 9.03, whereas the mean scores of independent variables *i.e.*, CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA are 15.01, 2.44 and 19.02 respectively.

Table 2.2 : Correlation coefficient among variables

		ROE	CAR	NPA	CAR/NPA
Pearson Correlation	ROE	1.000	0.805	-0.963	0.872
	CAR	0.805	1.000	-0.816	0.636
	NPA	-0.963	-0.816	1.000	-0.783
	CAR/NPA	0.872	0.636	-0.783	1.000
Significance (1-tailed)	ROE	-	-	-	-
	CAR	0.027*	-	-	-
	NPA	0.001*	0.024*	-	-
	CAR/NPA	0.012*	0.087	0.033*	.-

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

Table 2.2 displays the correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable (ROE) is correlated with CAR, NPA, and CAR/NPA, having correlation coefficients of 0.805, -0.963, and 0.872, respectively. Although ROE and NPA are inversely correlated; ROE, CAR, and CAR/NPA have a strong and favorable correlation. The results also exhibit a moderate correlation between the independent variables.

Table 2.3 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	ANOVA	
					F Change	Sig. Change
1	0.982	0.964	0.910	1.91316	17.863	0.05*
Predictors: (Constant), CAR/NPA, CAR, NPA						
Dependent Variable : ROE						

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

Table 2.3 provides the model summary wherein the independent variables predict the dependent variable (ROE) to a level of 96.4 percent based on the R-square value 0.964. The ANOVA findings show that the independent variables NPA, CAR, and CAR/NPA have a significant impact on ROE (dependent variable). Therefore, the null hypothesis ($H_{0.1}$), i.e., there is no significant impact of credit risk management on ROE of Indian banks, is rejected.

Table 2.4 : Coefficients of ROE

Model	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Significance	Collinearity Statistics	
	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-	0.875	0.047*	-	-
CAR	0.059	0.255	0.028*	0.334	2.994
NPA	-0.675	-2.346	0.014*	0.217	4.599
CAR/NPA	0.306	1.421	0.291	0.388	2.580

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

Table 2.4 depicts the coefficients of ROE and collinearity statistics, where all the Tolerance values for independent variables (CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA) are more than 0.10, which means that the Model has not violated the assumption of Multi-collinearity assumption. These results are also supported by the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values, which are less than 10. The analysis further shows that the coefficients of all the independent variables have been included in the model for prediction of the dependent variable. Standardized beta values are used to compare the contribution of each independent variable. The negative standardized beta coefficient implies an inverse relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables. The highest beta values i.e. 0.675 and 0.306 for NPA and CAR/NPA, respectively, indicate that these independent variables contributed maximum in explaining the dependent variable. The results of t-test indicate that the significance values of the independent variables (CAR and NPA) are less than 0.05, therefore it is concluded that contribution of independent variables is statistically significant in predicting the dependent variable.

3. Analysis of Impact of Credit Risk Management on ROA of Indian Banks

The impact of credit risk management on ROA of Indian banks for the period under study has been examined with the help of the following equation:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times CAR + \beta_2 \times NPA + \beta_3 \times CAR/NPA + e_1$$

Where,

ROA = Return on Assets of Indian Banks for the period of 2012-2022,

CAR = Capital Adequacy Ratio for the period of 2012-22,

NPA = Non-Performing Assets ratio for the period of 2012-22,

CAR/NPA = Capital Adequacy Ratio to Non-Performing Assets for the period of 2012-22,

β_0 = Intercept (Constant),

1	0.990	0.979	0.948	0.16371	31.315	0.031*
Predictors: (Constant), CAR/NPA, CAR, NPA						
Dependent Variable : ROA						

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

Table 3.3 provides a description of the model. The R-square value of 0.979 show that the independent variable predicts the dependent variable (ROA) to a level of 97.9 percent. The ANOVA findings show that the independent variables CAR, NPA, and CAR/NPA have a significant impact on ROA (dependent variable). Therefore, the null hypothesis ($H_{0.2}$) i.e. there is no significant impact of credit risk management on ROA of Indian banks, is rejected.

Table 3.4 : Coefficientsof ROA

Model	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Significance	Collinearity Statistics	
	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		-1.992	0.185		
1 CAR	0.543	3.075	.041*	0.334	2.994
NPA	-0.041	-0.188	.036*	0.217	4.599
CAR/NPA	0.510	3.112	.047*	0.388	2.580

Source : All the figures are computed with the help of SPSS20 version

Note: *Significant at 5 percent level

Table 3.4 depicts the coefficients of ROA and collinearity statistics, where all the Tolerance values for independent variables (CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA) are more than 0.10, which means that the Model has not violated the assumption of Multi-collinearity assumption. These results are also supported by the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values, which are less than 10. The analysis further shows that the coefficients of all the independent variables have been included in the model for prediction of the dependent variable. Standardized beta values are used to compare the contribution of each independent variable. The negative standardized beta coefficient implies an inverse relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables. The highest beta values i.e. 0.543 and 0.510 for CAR and CAR/NPA, respectively, indicate that these independent variables contributed maximum in explaining the dependent variable. The results of t-test indicate that the significance values of the independent variables (CAR, NPA and CAR/NPA) are less than 0.05, therefore it is concluded that contribution of independent variables is statistically significant in predicting the dependent variable.

Findings

The above analysis has been done with the help of data compiled from the various annual reports of the sample banks. In this regard, the findings of the study are as follows:

1. There is a significant impact of NPA, CAR, and CAR/NPA (independent variables) on ROE (dependent variable) of Indian banks. Therefore, the null hypothesis $H_{0.1}$ is rejected and alternate hypothesis $H_{1.1}$ is accepted.
2. There is a significant impact of NPA, CAR, and CAR/NPA (independent variables) on ROA (dependent variable) of Indian banks. Therefore, the null hypothesis $H_{0.2}$ is rejected and alternate hypothesis $H_{1.2}$ is accepted.

Conclusion

After analyzing the data, it is apparent that the financial performance of both the public and private sector banks is as fine as fiddle. However, a comparative analysis of data brings to view that private banks perform better than public sector banks because their CAR, ROA, and ROE ratios are better than those of the latter. This would imply that private banks are making better use of the investor's funds to create income. The return on assets ratio reveals another noteworthy difference that the private sector banks are producing higher returns on their assets in comparison to public banks. The CAR for private banks is

likewise higher, demonstrating their adequate capacity for absorbing risks. Moreover, in comparison to public sector banks, the NPA for private banks is quite low. Hence, the public sector banks must concentrate on minimizing their NPAs and improving their CAR in order to perform better. Thus, it can be contemplated that "Effective Credit Risk Management as a Tool for Sustainable Financial Performance in Banks is a reality and not a myth".

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Banks must concentrate on boosting non-interest income. To raise revenues, the banks must look to expand into a wide range of financial services, such as factoring, mutual funds, leasing, portfolio management, and merchant banking, which will open up the fresh sources of lucrative income for banks.
2. A substantial customer base has been captivated by the private banks due to their quick and effective working methods, attractive schemes, cutting-edge technologies, and superior customer service. Therefore, in order to provide effective customer services, public sector banks must also adopt the most recent advancements.
3. One of the most vital signs of a bank's financial health is the quality of its assets. Due to reduced levels of recovery, the new deposition of NPAs has been accumulating more rapidly than the reduction of existing NPAs. Therefore, banks must adhere to the appropriate mid-term credit assessment policy, supervise and track advances, improve asset quality, and implement an efficient internal control system in order to prevent NPAs. A significant diminution in NPAs is required to boost the profitability.
4. To reduce credit risks, banks must establish strong credit administration committees and teams, as well as adequate credit rules that meet all relevant requirements before giving credit to consumers. These committees and teams must undertake suitable and sound loan appraisal evaluations, as well as supervise the loan process from the time a loan is advanced until the time it is repaid.

Limitation of the Study

- The key limitations of the study are as follows:
1. This research is time bound and only certain criteria have been taken up for the study.
 2. All the computations have been done on the basis of data as at balance sheet date.
 3. The study revolves around 3 public sector and 3 private sector commercial banks representing Indian Banking Sector. Hence, findings may differ for other banks.
 4. The secondary data has its own limitations.

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References

1. Bagchi, S.K. (2004). Credit Risk Management (3rd edition.). Jaico Publishing House. <https://www.academia.edu/25124786/>
2. Dalvi Madhukar, & Shelankar Mitali. (2018). Impact of Credit Risk Management on the Financial Performance of selected Public and Private Sector Banks in India. RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary, 03(08), 883–889. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1407662>
3. Kaur, Ramanjeet (2020), "An Empirical Study of Credit Risk Management Practices of Commercial Banks in India", Department of Commerce, Guru Kashi University, Punjab. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/326875>
4. Kumar, Deepak (2018), "Impact of Credit Risk Management on Profitability and Liquidity of Public Sector Banks", Department of Business Administration, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/270862>
5. Mayank. (2021, September 23). A Guide to Credit Risk Management for Indian Banks. Retrieved from Lead Squared: <https://www.leadsquared.com/credit-risk-management/>
6. Nagar, Udhister (2019), "Credit risk management in commercial banks -A Critical Study of Selected Public and Private Sector Commercial Bank in India", Department of Accountancy and Business Statistics, University of Rajasthan, Rajasthan. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/334443>
7. Nikhil Kumar Shah, Nisarg Shah (2020) "A Credit Risk Management in Public and Private Sector Banks". JETIR, ISSN: 2349-5162. Volume 7, Issue 4. pp 607-615. www.jetir.org
8. Siddique, A., Khan, M.A. and Khan, Z. (2021), "The effect of credit risk management and bank-specific factors on the financial performance of the South Asian commercial banks", Asian Journal of Accounting Research, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-08-2020-0071>
9. Sundarka, Baibhav P. (2020), "Empirical Study of Credit Risk Management of Commercial Banks", Department of Management, Gujrat University, Gujrat. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/309018>
10. <https://www.axisbank.com/shareholders-corner/shareholders-information/annual-reports>
11. <https://www.bankofbaroda.in/shareholders-corner/annual-reports>
12. <https://www.hdfc.com/investor-relations#annual-reports>

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13. <https://www.icicibank.com/aboutus/annual.page>
14. <https://www.pnbindia.in/annual-reports.html>
15. <https://www.sbi.co.in/web/corporate-governance/annual-report>